

From quenched to gas-rich to star-forming: the diversity of faint dwarf galaxies

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In the past fifteen years, advances in wide-sky, photometric imaging have more than doubled the number of known, faint dwarf galaxies around the Milky Way (see [1] for a review; Figure 1). Thanks to their low masses and shallow potential wells, these faint systems are highly sensitive probes of the nature of dark matter – for example providing leading constraints on models modifying the abundance of small structures [2] – and of the physics of star formation and how stars "feedback" and affect their surrounding interstellar medium [3, 4, 5].

This new abundance of data, and the prospect of further discoveries and more detailed characterisations with next-generation wide, deep surveys (e.g., LSST, Euclid, the Nancy Roman Space Telescope) provides us with a unique opportunity to drastically improve our understanding of these physical processes. However, interpreting these observations requires accurate theoretical predictions, that pinpoints the properties of a population of faint dwarf galaxies in both its expected mean and scatter. Such requirement implies modelling a large number of objects, to sample many different histories and masses. This is however in direct conflict with the need to accurately resolve internal, astrophysical processes within these small objects. In this Hypatia colloquium, I present work addressing this challenge using a new approach [6, 7], part of the EDGE collaborative effort first introduced in [5].

We start by using high-resolution cosmological, galaxy formation simulations to compute each galaxy's observables. These hydrodynamical simulations are capable of resolving individual supernova explosions, thus significantly reducing uncertainties in the modelling of supernova feedback [5]. We then combine them with the genetic modification approach [8, 9, 10], which allows us to efficiently scan through possible cosmological mass growth histories. Genetic modifications create alternative, cosmological initial conditions for a given galaxy, modifying a specified aspect of its mass growth over time, while recreating the same large-scale structure and environment. Evolving each modified initial condition with our hydrodynamical setup then enables controlled, comparative experiments, building a causal account of how histories shape the dwarf's final observables.

This dual ability is key to our presented results, allowing us to cleanly isolate how (i) different early histories drive scatter in the stellar masses and sizes of field ultra-faints at fixed halo mass today (Section 1 and [6]); and (ii) how different late assemblies allow the re-accretion of gas and the re-ignition of very low-levels of star formation, similar to observed systems like Leo T and Leo P (Section 2 and [7]).

Figure 1: Response of the $z = 0$ total V-band magnitude and half-light radius of an ultra-faint dwarf when modifying its early growth history. Increasingly earlier-forming dwarfs (turquoise to purple) have larger stellar masses (smaller total V-band magnitude) and more compact sizes. Our latest forming history (turquoise) assembles through late, dry mergers, inflating its size and making it more diffuse (grey lines) than currently observed systems (points). Reproduced from Figure 3 in [6].

Generating scatter in stellar masses and surface brightnesses of ultra-faint dwarfs

We start with a series of four "genetically modified" initial conditions for a single object, varying its accretion history up to the time of cosmic reionization, while fixing its $z = 0$ dynamical mass. Figure 1 shows the response of the central galaxy's total V-band magnitude and half-light radius to these modifications.

By making this system systematically earlier forming (from turquoise to purple in Figure 1), we see that the dynamical mass assembled before reionization directly maps onto the final stellar mass of an ultra-faint. Earlier-forming galaxies begin forming stars when the universe was younger, and have a more vigorous star formation rate at a given time. They therefore assemble systematically higher stellar masses (smaller total magnitude), before further gas accretion is hampered by the build-up of cosmic photo-ionizing radiation as the Universe is reionized, leading to their permanent quenching [11]. Since by construction, all our histories converge to the same dynamical mass today, we cleanly show how the diversity of possible early histories leads to an extended scatter (1 dex) in the relation between stellar mass and halo mass of ultra-faints at $z = 0$.

Furthermore, our scan through histories reveals a highly diffuse dwarf (turquoise), arising from an early truncation of in-situ star formation due to reionization, but a later growth by dry mergers. These mergers deposit stars on wide orbits, vastly growing the final half-light radius. Such extremely diffuse systems lack counterparts in currently observed systems (points), but the recurring improvement toward lower surface brightnesses (grey lines; observations coloured by discovery year) should enable near-future surveys to test their existence.

Re-igniting star formation in faint dwarf galaxies

Extending from the previous results, we then focus on a suite of four faint dwarf galaxies hosted in dark matter halos with mildly increasing mass at $z = 0$ ($1.5 \times 10^9 \leq M_{200} \leq 3 \times 10^9 M_{\odot}$). All dwarf galaxies in our suite are still sufficiently small to be quenched by the reduction of gas inflows once cosmic reionization has heated their surrounding medium (Figure 2).

However, the two more massive objects both experience a re-ignition of star formation after $z = 1$. We link this rejuvenation to a slow re-accretion of gas after reionization ($z \leq 2$), steadily increasing the central gas mass of the dwarf until star-forming densities are eventually reached (Figure 2, blue). This re-accretion is triggered by a late growth in dynamical mass, which allows leftover gas within the halo to reach sufficient densities to cool and condense efficiently.

However, because of the low gas masses within these dwarfs, we find that small energy inputs from old stars (Type Ia explosions and winds from AGB stars) can balance the cooling of gas and lengthen the quiescent period by several billion years (brown). Furthermore, we show that this feedback barrier strongly interacts with the given assembly of the dwarf. We, for example, achieve to restart star formation in a quiescent object by either reducing feedback strength or growing its final dynamical mass using genetic modifications.

Neutral gas in faint dwarfs

We have shown examples of (i) gas-rich, low-mass dwarfs with ongoing star formation (e.g., blue in Figure 2), (ii) low-mass dwarfs caught in transition, exhibiting an exclusively old stellar population but a sizeable gas content (e.g., brown in Figure 2), and (iii) gas-poor, quenched low-mass dwarfs (e.g., black in Figure 2). All three galaxies have stellar and dark matter halo masses within a factor of two, demonstrating extended scatter in gas content and stellar ages within low-mass dwarfs due to the coupling between feedback and late assemblies.

This uncovered diversity strongly motivates a quantification of the neutral gas observables across our simulated suite of dwarf galaxies. In fact, matching radio observations with deep imaging has already provided ev-

idence for both star-forming and non-star-forming, gas-rich faint dwarfs [12, 13]. The prospect of combining ever-deeper photometric facilities with next-generation radio facilities (e.g., SKA) further warrants investigating the relationship between stellar and HI content at the faint end. Presenting preliminary results, I showed how the diversity of histories and final masses in our suite leads to order-of-magnitude scatter in neutral gas content at fixed stellar mass today.

Figure 2: Evolution of the central gas mass for three simulated dwarfs with increasing halo mass today (black to brown to blue). All dwarfs see their gas inflows heavily reduced following reionization ($z \approx 4$), but a late growth in dynamical mass triggers slow re-accretion of gas (blue and brown). If rapid enough, this accretion allows the re-ignition of star formation before $z = 0$ (blue, but not brown). Reproduced from Figure 2 in [7].

References

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